

Physical Characteristics of Female Student Players of Badminton Studying in Pakistani Universities

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 23, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 29, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Female Student Player, Badminton, Physical Parameters, Anthropometric Parameters, Pakistan</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5807907</p>	<p><i>Players are usually classified based on physical parameters. The body composition of a player is a significant factor for the success in the game. The main objective of the study was to examine the physical characteristic of female badminton players at university levels. Primary data were collected from 30 female student players of badminton belonging to the University of Agriculture Faisalabad (n=10), Government College University Faisalabad (n=10), and Government College Women University Faisalabad (n=10). Physical parameters like upper leg length, lower leg length, foot length, and triceps skinfold and anthropometric characteristics such as height, weight, body mass index, lean body mass, and fat were measured. Results revealed that the average age of female badminton players was found 23.20 years, average weight (63.10 kg), average height (5.34 feet), BMI (33.99), LBM (33.99), and average body fat (29.10). The findings indicated that upper leg length was 45.07 cm, lower leg length (40.67cm), foot length (25.93 cm), and triceps skinfold (23.82 mm). It was concluded that physical and anthropometric characteristics were found up to the mark of female student players of badminton. The coaches should train female players according to their physical and anthropometric capacities to gain maximal outcomes.</i></p>

Introduction

Badminton is a popular sport all around the world. Many Asian countries now consider it their national sport. This game may be played by anyone of any age or ability level and it is considered among the fastest racket games (Angga, 2019). Badminton is a game that requires a high level of natural ability as well as a wide range of pressure in aggressive games. It is a sport with a lot of short-duration but high-intensity game actions, as well as several different movements and shuttlecock strokes (Ranzmeyer & Niesner, 2017).

In badminton, anthropometric factors are most important to achieve great success (Sanchez-Munoz et al., 2020; Abdullahi et al., 2017). Anthropometric measurements are used to create links between bone mass and body structure (Abian, Abian-Vicen, & Sampedro, 2012). Anthropometric measurements are frequently used to categorize players based on their age or level of performance (Abraham, 2010). In badminton, height is an advantage when it comes to completing attacking strokes (Angga, 2019). In team games, it is especially important to pick team members that match specified body constitution criteria (Robertson-Martens, 2021). The anthropometric measurements were introduced in 1883 by Alphonse Bertillon. Each human could be identified from others based on these measurements (Cuff, 2019).

The performance will undoubtedly improve if the instructor has a good understanding of the biology and morphology of the human body. The anthropometric measurement is the primary requirement of different constitutional challenges faced by the players before every experience of the game (Eston, & Reilly, 2018). Maud and Foster (2006) explained how to quantify the domains for scale, dimensional proportions, weight, frame size, figure, and associated frame design. One of the important predictors of strength is to measure biological characteristics to analyze the shape of a player (Kuczmariski, Kuczmariski, & Najjar, 2000). It could help in the determination of the weight, body-building, boy proportion, and magnitude in relation to body mass. In sports competitions, good performance is necessary for final achievement. Ayodele and Akinbiola (2018) looked at the physiological differences between male and female Nigerian football players as well as the players' anthropometrical and physiological profiles (Mishra, 2016; Nande, 2014).

It has been projected that regular sports, physical exercise, and physical health have a substantial association (Abdullahi et al., 2017). Badminton is generally a game of various movements of high intensity combined with little resting time (Reilly & Kipps, 2018). In badminton game, variety of strategic possibilities are considered. Special arrangements for the persistence of the player can be made during the game combined with control and some specific motor actions.

For enhanced performance, badminton players need tremendous ability, agility, aerobic capacity, and explosive power. A player's body composition is an important aspect of fitness. In sports like badminton, the

player's weight must be lifted repeatedly against gravity. Extra body fat might be harmful to a player's performance. The goal of the study was to highlight the specific characteristics and elements that influence playing skills. Because physical characteristics are essential elements in performance and fitness, whereas, anthropometric variables are directly linked to motor performance (Sanchez-Munoz, Sanz, & Zabala, 2007; Wan-Nudri, Ismail, & Zawiak, 1996). Anthropometric measurement and exercise are important for badminton player (Nordstrom, Högström, & Nordström, 2008; Perissinotto et al., 2002).

Objectives of the Study

Keeping in view the anthropometric measurements, the following objective of the study was established:

i: To investigate the physical characteristics of female student players of badminton at universities level of Pakistan.

Methodological Procedures

The study area of the current study was Faisalabad city of Punjab province of Pakistan. Female student players of badminton were selected studying in three universities of Faisalabad (University of Agriculture Faisalabad, Government College University Faisalabad, and Government College Women University Faisalabad). In order to meet the study's objective, a total of 30 female student players of badminton were chosen who participated in intervarsity competitions. Ten players were selected from each university.

Data were collected by using different tools. The present research was conducted by measuring the anthropometric characteristics of female student players of badminton. Various anthropometrical variables were assessed including weight, height, BMI, LBM, and percentage of fat. Badminton coaches assisted the researchers in making contact with badminton players in order to collect the desired data. Permission was obtained from each participant on an individual basis.

The following are anthropometric estimates of essential body parts for players:

Tallness

The height was calculated by measuring the distance between the top of the head and the ground. Study participants were instructed to stand in a perpendicular anatomical position with closed feet together, laterally hanging their arms perpendicular. A measuring tape was used to quantify a player's height while standing against the wall (Abdullahi et al., 2017).

Weight

A weighting machine was utilized to measure the weight of players in very light garments nearest the value of 0.1 kg (Heymsfield et al., 2018).

Deskbound Height

Deskbound Height was determined by adjusting the chair to ensure proper sitting posture. Make sure the player is sitting comfortably and do not tense or elevate her shoulders. Now take a measurement from the bottom of your elbow to the floor. This is your personal desk height, which you can alter at your desk (Usman et al., 2018).

Formula: $\frac{\text{Sitting Height} \times 100}{\text{Height}}$

Height

Body Mass Index (BMI)

The body mass index (BMI) is the most extensively used metric for classifying and determining anthropometric attributes (Locke et al., 2015). It is a measurement of a person's fatness. It is calculated by dividing the height by the weight of a person (Nuttall, 2015).

$\text{BMI} = \frac{\text{Height (m}^2\text{)}}{\text{Weight (kg)}}$

Lean Body Mass (LBM)

The fat-free portion of the body is measured by lean body mass. It is derived by subtracting the fat percentage from total body weight.

Body Fat

By subtracting the value of lean body mass from total body weight, body fat can be computed.

Triceps Skin Fold

The measurement of skinfold thickness is commonly used to quantify body fat. Skinfold measurement is commonly used to track changes in body composition as a result of training and/or nutritional modifications. The measurement of the skin fold was taken after 4 seconds. The mean of the three readings was used to calculate the final score (Heymsfield et al., 2018).

Upper Leg Length

The leg is placed on the table for the upper leg length measurement. The lower part of the right leg hangs freely over the table's edge while the right knee is bent at a 90-degree angle. There was a gap between these two markers, which was observed. Reduce the leg length measurement to the nearest 0.1 cm (Heymsfield et al., 2018).

Lower Leg Length

The lower leg length of female badminton players was measured from the top of the kneecap to the underside of the foot. The player was seated at a 90-degree angle with their knees bent (Akodu & Akindele, 2020).

Foot Length

Foot length was measured after standing the player on flat surface. With a measuring tape, trace the outline from the rear of the heel to the end of the longest toe. The measurements were taken three times for a more precise result (Heymnsfield et al., 2018).

The collected data from female student players of three universities belonging to Faisalabad was edited. The statistical data was analyzed further through descriptive analysis (frequencies and percentages)

Findings and Discussion

Age is an important factor that influences the performance of a player. Among female badminton players age significantly affects the upper body strength (Cinhuja et al., 2015). Table 1 depicts the age groups of female badminton players. The average age of the female badminton players was 23.20 years. In the first category, 9 out of 30 players were between the ages of 21 and 22 years. The majority of the players fell under the 23-24 years of age bracket. Only three players were beyond the age of 24 years.

Table 1

Distribution of players with respect to their age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
21-22	9	30.0
23-24	18	60
25-26	3	10
Total	30	100

In badminton, the bodyweight is used to be lifted repeatedly against gravity and extra fat mass would hurt performance (Phomsoupha & Laffaye, 2015). According to Yuksel and Tunc (2018), there is no substantial difference in female badminton players' weight all around the world. And the average weight was 60.62 kilograms. The weight in this trial was a little higher than usual. Because of COVID-19, the universities were closed, a lack of regular practice and exercise could be the cause of the increased weight. Figure 1 shows that 66.6% of players weigh between 64 and 73 kilograms. The mean weight was 63.10 with a standard deviation of 8.43 kg.

Figure 1. Weight of female badminton players

Height is supposed to be beneficial in terms of dominating every region of the court, although it is unclear whether height is beneficial in badminton (Ozgun & Hotaman, 2020). In a similar study, no significant association between height and badminton performance was discovered (Omveer, 2017). The mean height of female badminton players was 5.34 with a standard deviation of 0.1758, as shown in Table 2. More than half of the players were between the ages of 5.3 and 5.4 according to the results.

Table 2

Distribution of players with respect to their height (feet-inches)

Height (ft-inch)	Frequency	Percentage
5.1-5.2	09	30.0
5.3-5.4	16	53.4
5.5-5.6	03	10

5.7-5.8	02	6.6
Total	30	100.0

Female badminton players had a mean BMI of 33.993 and a standard deviation of 4.87. Total 63.3% of players had a BMI in the 23-36 range, 20.10% had in the 19-22 range, 13.2% players found BMI in the 27-30 range, and 3.3% females were BMI in the 15-18 range.

Figure 2. Female badminton players are distributed according to their BMI.

Lean body mass (LBM) is considered the most important determinant of performance ability. Medium enhancement in lean body mass may cause to increase the better speed, strength, and power without forfeiting the elasticity or volatile force. The mean LBM of female players was 33.99 with a standard deviation of 4.879. The LBM of players was 66.2% within the 34-39 range, players with 16.6% were considered in the range 29-27, about 10% were ranged 28-33 and 6.6% were of the 40-46 LBM range.

Table 3

Distribution of Players with respect to their Lean Body Mass

Lean Body Mass	Frequency	Percentage
29-27	5	16.6
28-33	3	9.9
34-39	20	66.2
40-46	2	6.6
Total	30	100.0

Conclusion and Implications

Physical and anthropometric characteristics play an important role in performing well in any game. Female badminton players' physical and anthropometric characteristics were measured in this study. Upper leg length, lower leg length, foot length, and triceps skinfold are all physical criteria to consider. The results showed that the average upper leg length was 45.07 cm, lower leg length was 40.67 cm, foot length was 25.93 cm, and triceps skinfold was 23.82 mm. Anthropometric characteristics like height, weight, and body mass index, lean body mass, and fat were measured. Results showed that average weight was 63.10 kg, average height was 5.34 feet, BMI was 33.99, LBM was 33.99 and average body fat was 29.10.

Anthropometric parameters have a greater impact on the performance of female badminton players. The players' physical composition must be taken into account while developing a training program. Qualified coaches should be deputized to measure the physical structure of individual athletes so that they may design a comprehensive workout program appropriate to female players. Future research may focus on the development of new criterion approaches for measuring regional body composition accurately. Future studies could include female badminton players from other cities or provinces of Pakistan.

References

- Abdullahi, Y., Toriola, A.L., Goon, D.T., Paul, Y., Igbokwe, N.U., & Suarau, M.A. (2017). Anthropometric and motor performance characteristics of Nigerian badminton players. *Asian Journal of Scientific Research*, 10(3), 244-251. DOI:[10.3923/ajsr.2017.244.251](https://doi.org/10.3923/ajsr.2017.244.251)
- Abian, P., Abian-Vicen, J., & Sampedro, J. (2012). Anthropometric analysis of body symmetry in badminton players. *International Journal of Morphology*, 30(3), 945-951. DOI:<http://dx.doi.org/10.4067/S0717-95022012000300030>
- Abraham, G. (2010). Analysis of anthropometry, body composition and performance variables of young Indian athletes in southern region. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(12), 1210-1213. DOI:[10.17485/ijst/2010/v3i12/29864](https://doi.org/10.17485/ijst/2010/v3i12/29864)
- Akodu, A.K., & Akindele, O. A. (2020). Limb length discrepancy and gait parameters of amateur football players in Lagos State, Nigeria. *South African Journal of Sports Medicine*, 32(1), 1-3. DOI:[10.17159/2078-516X/2020/v32i1a8029](https://doi.org/10.17159/2078-516X/2020/v32i1a8029)
- Angga, P.D. (2019). *Anthropometric and motor performance of junior badminton athlete*. In 2nd International Conference on Sports Sciences and Health 2018 (2nd ICSSH 2018) (pp. 143-146). Atlantis Press.
- Ayodele, R.B., & Akinbiola, O.O. (2018). Dance, physical fitness and nation building: What relationship? *European Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science*, 4(10), 147-156. Doi:10.5281/zenodo.1451725
- Cinthuja, P., Jayakody, J.A.O.A., Perera, M.P.M., Weerathna, W.V.D.N., Nirosha, S.E., Indeewari, D.K.D.C. ... & Adikari, S.B. (2015). Physical fitness factors of school badminton players in Kandy district. *European Journal of Sports and Exercise Science*, 4(2), 14-25.
- Cuff, T. (2019). Introduction: Historical anthropometrics - theory, method, and the state of the field. In *the biological standard of living on three continents* (pp. 1-15). Routledge.
- Eston, R. & Reilly, T. (2018). *Kinanthropometry and exercise physiology laboratory manual: Test, procedures and data*. Routledge.
- Heymsfield, S.B., Bourgeois, B., Ng, B.K., Sommer, M.J., Li, X., & Shepherd, J.A. (2018). Digital anthropometry: A critical review. *European Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 72(5), 680-687.
- Kuczmarski, R.J., & Najjar, M. (2000). Descriptive anthropometric reference data for older Americans. *Journal of the American Dietetic Association*, 100(1), 59-66. DOI:[10.1016/S0002-8223\(00\)00021-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-8223(00)00021-3)
- Locke, A.E., Kahali, B., Berndt, S.I., Justice, A.E., Pers, T.H., Day, F.R. ... & Lindström, J. (2015). Genetic studies of body mass index yield new insights for obesity biology. *Nature*, 518, 197-206. doi: 10.1038/nature14177.
- Maud, P.J., & Foster, C. (2006). Physiological assessment of human fitness. *Human Kinetics*.
- Mishra, P.K. (2016). A comparative study of selected anthropometric measurements between badminton and table-tennis players of Sardar Patel University. *International Journal of Physical Education, Sports and Health*, 3(6), 69-71.
- Nande, P.J. (2014). Anthropometric measurements, dietary intake and lipid profile of hypertensive young adults (25-35 years): A comparison between vegetarians and non vegetarians. *Current Research in Nutrition and Food Science*, 2(3), 122-130. DOI:<http://dx.doi.org/10.12944/CRNFSJ.2.3.03>
- Nordstrom, A., Höglström, M., & Nordström, P. (2008). Effects of different types of weight-bearing loading on bone mass and size in young males: A longitudinal study. *Bone*, 42(3), 565-571. doi: 10.1016/j.bone.2007.11.012.
- Nuttall, F.Q. (2015). Body mass index, obesity, BMI, and health: A critical review. *Nutrition Today*, 50(3), 117-128. doi: 10.1097/NT.0000000000000092
- Omveer. (2017). A study on prediction of playing ability in badminton from selected anthropometrical physical and physiological characteristics among inter collegiate players. *International Journal of Advanced Research and Development*, 2(5), 50-54.
- Ooi, C.H., Tan, A. Ahmad, A., Kwong, K.W., Sompong, R., Ghazali, K.A.M., ... & Thompson, M.W. (2009). Physiological characteristics of elite and sub-elite badminton players. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 27(14), 1591-1599. DOI:[10.1080/02640410903352907](https://doi.org/10.1080/02640410903352907)
- Ozgur, B., & Hotaman, F. (2020). Relationship between physical performance and unforced error during the competition in national Turkish junior badminton players. *International Journal of Applied Exercise Physiology*, 9(7), 144-151.
- Perissinotto, E., Pisent, C., Sergi, G., Grigoletto, F., & Enzi, G. (2002). Anthropometric measurements in the elderly: Age and gender differences. *British Journal of Nutrition*, 87(2), 177-186. DOI:10.1079/BJN2001487
- Phomsoupha, M., & Laffaye, G. (2015). The science of badminton: Game characteristics, anthropometry, physiology, visual fitness and biomechanics. *Sports Medicine*, 45(4), 473-495. DOI:[10.1007/s40279-014-0287-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-014-0287-2)

- Ranzmeyer, J. & Niesner, H.W. (2017). Coming to Grips with Reality. *Science Robotics*, 6(54), eabi9225. DOI: 10.1126/scirobotics.abi9225
- Reilly, J., & Kipps, C. (2018). The implementation and adoption of the injury prevention exercise programme GAA 15 in Gaelic football club teams in the counties of Mayo and London. *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 51(4), 377-377. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2016-097372.237>
- Robertson-Martens, K. (2021). *Multidisciplinary contributions to talent identification in young elite badminton players* (Doctoral dissertation). Ghent University.
- Sanchez-Munoz, C., Muros, J.J., Canas, J., Courel-Ibanez, J., Sánchez-Alcaraz, B.J., & Zabala, M. (2020). Anthropometric and physical fitness profiles of world-class male padel players. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(2), 508. DOI: [10.3390/ijerph17020508](https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17020508)
- Sanchez-Munoz, C., Sanz, D., & Zabala, M. (2007). Anthropometric characteristics, body composition and somatotype of elite junior tennis players. *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 41(11), 793-799. DOI: [10.1136/bjism.2007.037119](https://doi.org/10.1136/bjism.2007.037119)
- Usman, B., Champion, I., Muslem, A., & Samad, I. A. (2018). Standing, active vs sitting, torpid: A management decision. *Al-Ta'Lim Journal*, 25(1), 22-35. DOI: [10.15548/jt.v25i1.378](https://doi.org/10.15548/jt.v25i1.378)
- Chinnaiyan, R. (2012). Relationship of arm length, shoulder strength, skill performance and badminton playing ability. *Star International Journal*, 3(10), 16-19.
- Wan-Nudri, W.D., Ismail, M.N., & Zawiak, H. (1996). Anthropometric measurements and body composition of selected national athletes. *Malaysian Journal of Nutrition*, 2(2), 138-147.
- Yuksel, M.F., & Tunc, G.T. (2018). Examining the reaction times of international level badminton players under 15. *Sports*, 6, 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.3390/sports6010020>

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